

Choose your Poison: The Company Store vs. Data Colonialism as a Means of Understanding the Exploitative Potential of Asymmetry in Data Collection and Service Provision

*You load 16 tons, what do you get?
Another day older and deeper in debt
St. Peter, don't you call me 'cause I can't go
I owe my soul to the company store*

-Merle Travis

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Outline

- Colonialism model and how it operated.
 - Critique of the metaphor of “data colonialism.”
 - Suggest a more accurate model for understanding how big technology companies operate.
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Colonialism

- Colonialism is a practice of domination, which involves the subjugation of one people to another (Stanford Encyclopedia).
 - The policy of a nation seeking to extend or retain its authority over other people or territories (Webster Encyclopedia Dictionary)
 - The practice by which a powerful country directly controls less powerful countries and uses their resources to increase its own power and wealth (Colins English Dictionary).
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What is *Data Colonialism*?

- Scholars call this *data colonialism*.
 - The process by which everyday human life is appropriated through data for profit and control by global corporations (Couldry and Mejias, 2019)
 - A means of capitalist accumulation by dispossession which colonizes and commodifies everyday life in ways previously impossible. (Thatcher and Mahmoudi, 2016)
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Is Colonialism the Right *Metaphor*?

Limits of the Colonialism Metaphor

- No violent conquest or foreign rule: no “over there” that is being colonised for “home” market
 - Digital users choose to participate (under pressure).
 - Control is mostly local and economic (not territorial).
 - Doesn't fully explain operations of modern tech systems.
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The Company Town Model...

- Process whereby a **single firm** issued the IDs (**user accounts**), provided its employees with goods and services, hired police (**algorithms**), collected garbage (**harmful or unwanted content**), dispensed justice (**content moderation decisions**), and answered (or failed to answer) complaints from residents (**users reporting issues or policy violations**). It also built the roads (**platform infrastructure**), maintained the town square (**newsfeeds and timelines**), and taxed its citizens with their attention (**advertising and data extraction**).
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Platform Capitalism as Company Town

- Users provide data = labor.
 - Platforms monetize this data = employer rent.
 - Users consume services within same platform = scrip economy.
 - Governance via ToS = illusion of agency
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User → Market → Miner

- Node A: User creates data
 - Node B: Data is sold to advertisers
 - Node C: User buys access to content shaped by advertiser data
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Why *Company Town* Fits Today's Digital World

- Tech firms provide “free” services and extract data.
 - Platforms control almost everything (rules, access, and content.)
 - Users can't easily leave (digital lock-in.)
 - Power is centralized yet disguised as a choice.
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Colonialism vs. Company Store in Platform Logic: A Comparison

	Colonial Model	Company Store Model
Spatial Relation	Distant: Core <i>Geographic</i> ↔ Periphery <i>separation</i>	Localized: User <i>Intimate</i> ↔ Platform <i>proximity</i>
Consent Mechanism	Violent/Subjugative <i>Overt force</i>	Contractual/Illusory <i>Terms of service</i>
Economic Circuit	Extract → Export → Profit <i>Linear extraction</i>	Extract → Resell → Rent → Repeat <i>Circular exploitation</i>
Agency Illusion	Complete Erasure <i>No pretense of choice</i>	Gamified Consent <i>Illusion of participation</i>

Value Flow: Colonialism vs Company Store

Colonial Value Flow

Company Store Value Flow

Takeaway

- Company town model captures and explains the power asymmetry and data appropriation in today's tech corporations better.
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Thank You

- Co-inhabitants of Company Town
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